

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

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THE THREAT OF LANGUAGE LOSS IN THE ERA OF GLOBALIZATION AND WAYS TO PREVENT IT

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Annotation: *With the advent of globalization, national languages are experiencing big loss under the threat of dominant global languages such as English, Spanish and Chinese. This article aims to explore main key factors which lead to this outcoming issue putting emphasize to some spheres: urbanization, digitalization and changes in educational priorities. Additionally, this study analyzes how social media and mass communication plays an important role to influence language preferences appealing younger generations to learn them. The article offers some potential solutions encompassing government policies, educational awareness, the promotion of digital language usage, and the usage of multifaceted of media and family interactions. Through these strategic efforts, societies not only can preserve their national language diversity, but also showcase the cultural and historical significance of national languages in this increasingly interconnected world.*

Keywords: *Language endangerment, national language, educational awareness, government policies, cultural identities, language loss, language patterns, abbreviations, acronyms, initialisms, Nollywood English.*

Introduction: Language itself is a set of different symbols and signs that is created by specific communities in the purpose of communication, interaction and self-expressions.

There is main three factors of globalization which contribute to the language endangerment including culture, economy and technology. One of the most visible effects of the cultural globalization is the rise of international sporting events such as Olympics, World Cup, international football tournament bringing people together with different social and linguistic backgrounds. For example, clubs like Manchester United and Real Madrid consist of the players from different continents appealing fans from all the corners of the world despite being established in England and Madrid. Secondly, celebrities, film and music have a part to play in the cultural globalizations promoting K-pop, Hollywood films, international music icons and K-dramas among youngsters. The main characters in these productions often come same with the desire of most young generations embracing their fashion trends, cultural expressions and linguistic trends in which, often leads to eject traditional customs and heritage. Additionally, leaders have started to understand that they should learn

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cultural identities if they want to establish strong business in global market. By doing so, they gradually can implement their own products to local markets all of which leads to similar consumption patterns globally, bringing its own language to the trade. Alibaba, Amazon can be a good example of international shopping site, which combines the people under the same purpose and specialized for only dominant languages. In some cases, international migration in the purpose of education, economic opportunities and travelling can cause cultural exchanges. For example, a person who has gone developed country like America from developing countries starts to integrate with cultural preferences of the place due to the strong atmosphere, respect towards improving society and language dominancy which usually leads to decrease the value of national culture. In economic sphere, most large companies often search cheaper labor forces to organize their businesses which is usually found in under developing countries. As well as the company boundaries, the life style of newcomers will be introduced to the local societies. Furthermore, import and export of goods among countries can have big impact on them, yet, which may lead to bankrupt of local businesses as they have cheaper and high-quality alternatives. Lastly, modernized technologies are mainly produced in developed countries like the USA, Japan, China and the South Korea which helps them to program it in their own language being the best way to encourage foreigners to learn them in order to know how to use new inventions.

In this digital era, dominant languages: English, Spanish, Chinese, Japan, German and Korean have been the most spoken languages all over the world exceeding in number of speakers day by day. These developing countries are putting much effort and investing a lot for their language in order to make it international spoken language and become more predominant for standing at the top of economic ladder. This, without any doubt, can bring popularity to the country itself, since people wants to travel the place where they know local language and culture to get more experience. Additionally, most of the people who wants to learn second languages firstly pay attention to its reputation in the world ranking and the opportunities it can offer including socio-economic benefits. For example, almost half of the world population learn English language as a second language as it can provide more future expectations. Showing India are known for hosting a hundred of local languages, despite this richness, the government is prioritizing English and Hindi with the choice of citizens, even adjusting the education system to cope with them. Furthermore, this language has stood in the first place of the world education system, being taught in schools and required certain degrees in knowing English language by

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labelling certificates in order to study international and certain national universities. Moreover, language proficiency is asked from the applicant who wants to get a job with high salary. This, in the fast pace, is attracting more and more young generations to learn it.

There are 7 billion people in the world and every nation has their own language to use in a specific area. But in order to unite people under the control of one special country, governments have implemented one language for one state. As a result, a lot of languages have started to face extinction, not being used in both official and unofficial spheres. India and China can a good example here since they are known as the most overpopulated countries as well as the big number of minor languages. Although the English language is not native, In India it should be used as a means of communication when people meet with different linguistic backgrounds. In China Mandarin language has been put into use when China achieved independence in 1949, having been protected and developed since then. However, firstly, other exist languages and dialects in the country have put barriers for the spread of it, encompassing a large portion of the population like Shanghai, Beijing, Guangzhou. Due to persistent initiatives by authorities, people have started to understand high future opportunities that comes from Mandarin language and accepted it as their own mother tongue. Now Mandarin language is one of the most widely adopted languages because of young generations and better educated adults who are being grown in the completely different atmosphere compared to their old relatives. It shows that local languages may extinct in China when new generations replace the last ones, meaning that, most languages need to reach an official and international level to flourish more.

It has been common among young people that the willingness to use foreign language has increasingly shifted from a means of acquiring knowledge to a marker of social prestige, largely due to the weakness of education system in teaching national language. They have started to speak foreign languages to show their strong intelligence in language learning, not their mother tongue as a pride. This is because most students are encouraged to learn other languages when they are in the kindergarten by giving them new dreams to achieve in foreign lands, especially developed countries but they do not know the real meaning and value of their own language, causing the decrease of interests towards learning it. In addition to it, due to the lack of necessary academic materials and books in certain fields, students will be compelled to search new information in another language, facing difficulties in translation to understand its meaning deeply. This can overwhelmingly motivate growing youngsters to be more fluent in other languages rather than mastering their

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own language. For example, when they start to talk in a strange language among the crowd, they start to feel their dominance over others because of impressing eyes and can be stimulated in continuing to learn it deeply.

Finally, social media and mass media mostly impact how our language patterns change, creating different opportunities for global communication. Apps like Instagram, Telegram, Facebook, Twitter can bring most young people together with their attractive programs and alive, appealing atmosphere, giving them a good choice to find like-minded friends globally. While they have undeniable benefits for youngsters, we should also admit some drawbacks that comes together with it, mainly for language evolution. The brevity required by social media, particularly on platforms like Twitter, which originally limited posts to 140 characters, has led to the widespread use of abbreviations, acronyms, and initialisms. Phrases like LOL (laugh out loud), OMG (Oh My God), "OK boomer", "YOLO" (you only live once), and "FOMO" (fear of missing out) have become common in online communication. This growing tendency toward laconicism and efficiency in digital interaction can impact on language proficiency in real world by eroding the boundary between social media and every day interactions. They are also using more relaxed grammar rules instead of adhering to standard ones in informal communication leading to the confusion of grammatical accuracy. For example, it is often seen that subjects and prepositions in the sentence are dropped while writing like "Going to store" instead of "I am going to the store" or nouns may be used as a verb (to Google, to friend), leading to the faster adaptation. For example, one research conducted in 2013 by Crystal detected that an average British teenager uses up to 800 different slang terms, many of which born out of internet culture. Since English language is a main means of communication in digital world, this language is experiencing new cultural phrases including "selfie" and effecting other languages internationally. As an example, although there are over 500 languages in Nigeria, with the rise of mobile technology "Nollywood English" has appeared and has been common among population. This trend also can be observed in other countries where English is learned as a second language or taught in schools or universities. Additionally, pragmatics, or the study of how context influences the interpretation of language, is also significantly affected by social media. The use of emojis, GIFs, and memes adds layers of meaning to text-based communication, providing visual and contextual cues that help convey tone, emotion, and intent. Emojis in general context has become globally common, enriching digital communication with visual content and making texts more interesting and touchable, yet causing faster linguistic shifts. Milner (2016) highlights that the viral nature of

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social media allows for the swift dissemination and adoption of new linguistic trends, significantly accelerating the pace of language evolution.

Solution: The preservation of indigenous languages is essential to maintaining cultural diversity and sustaining the unique worldviews and identities of indigenous communities. Government intervention is one of the key factors in language preservation as it plays an important role to promote social cohesion and raise people's awareness of the importance of obeying to linguistic policies. If authorities take everything into account such as economic, political, social and other conditions of other minor languages in the country before enacting law, they can contribute to the preservation, protection and development of them, enhancing their status and ensuring their prosperity by overshadowing direct threats of extinction. A good example of this phenomenon can be seen in Russia, possessing the largest area and structure with 85 constituent entities, including 20 republics. There are hundreds of minor languages in Russia with different ethnic groups such as Tatar (5.35 million speakers), Bashkir (1.38 million), Chechen and Chuvash (1.33 million each), having the rights to be spoken and used by the speakers independently. Although Russian is considered as official language through the country, constituent republics have the right to use their own language parallel with Russian on governing bodies. They can publish federal and republican rules and policies in those languages, also using in elections, referendums and industrial, judicial activities, all of which because of the rules in the Constitution of Russian Federation guaranteeing all its peoples the preservation of their ethnic language, and prerequisites for its study and development.

Next revolution for language protection will be the introduction of it into social media platforms, as currently dominant global languages have strong presence on the internet providing users with access to the unlimited information, educational resources and real-time updates. This widespread availability allows speakers to search anything in their own language and achieve their purpose easily in short time. However, other minority languages which are non-existent in digital sphere make it difficult for speakers to keep up with the times, staying unaware of last updates. By creating various contents, information, videos and uploading books in their own language, nations can increase internet accessibility making its society more knowledgeable. This can undoubtedly remain no need to rely on other global languages to find necessary information, increasing language value among nations. Apart from this, families play a crucial role in shaping language preferences, since they pass down their own cultural heritage and language to younger generations. If a particular language is not valued or used in the house, a growing child may not show

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interest to learn it later in life. The rules and ways of using native language can also affect how they use that language since the language which express love, tradition, happiness is mostly chosen to speak continuously. This shows that if society wants to foster their language during most centuries, they should nurture their child truly with the affection of language, tradition culture and family interaction, so that nothing can appeal them to forget their native language, by understanding the real value of it in self-recognition.

Conclusion: In the era of globalization, the spread of global languages including Spanish, English and Mandarin have been dominant over other national languages leading them to be faded. This is mainly due to poor education system of teaching local languages, less use of languages in social and mass media and other aspects of globalization causing less usage in both official and unofficial spheres. As a result, not only the value of national languages has been decreased among young generations, increasing famous language preferences, but also cultural identity, tradition, customs that comes with it have been mixed because of internet culture. To counteract this outcoming problems, government interaction can be the best solution by implementing strict policies to preserve it and drawing attention to teaching country language deeply by enhancing education system. Furthermore, families have strong boundaries to foster linguistic pride by ensuring that children grow up valuing their mother tongue. Ultimately, preserving national languages is not generally obligation, but a necessity for keeping linguistic diversity and national identity. By doing so, upcoming generations will be brought up under the feeling of love, honor, pride toward national language, tradition and cultural heritage, increasing the popularity of country itself.

Imagine If we try our best to make our language widely recognized, how would we envision our lives and in what status our country would be?!

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